

SAPONIFICATION OF ACETYLURETHANE AND ACETYL-SUBSTITUTED UREAS

BY M. N. DESAI AND C. M. DESAI

Saponification of acetylurethane, acetylphenyl-, acetyl-*m*-tolyl-, acetyl-*p*-tolyl-, acetyl-*p*-anisyl-, acetyl-*p*-xylyl-, and acetyl-*m*-phenetyl-carbamido was carried out by alcoholic potassium hydroxide, at 28° and 38° and the rate constants were calculated by the second order equation. The results are explained on the basis of the effect of substituents in the nucleus on hydrolysis reaction in the side-chain giving electronic interpretation. The effect of the substituents in the nucleus on the side-chain hydrolysis reaction is in the following decreasing order: *m*-OEt < H < *m*-Me < *p*-Me > *p*-OMe.

Kinetic study of saponification of esters can be traced back for more than half a century. A study of the effect of substitution on the rate determining factors in case of different esters was, however, recently carried out by many investigators (Evans, Gordon and Watson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1439; Smith and Levenson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 1172, 1963; Shrivastava, this *Journal*, 1940, 19, 387); in these studies kinetic data have been interpreted in the light of the application of the equation,

$$k = PZ e^{-\frac{E}{RT}}$$

Ramart, Naik and collaborators (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1934, 1, 525; this *Journal*, 1938, 17, 426; 1943, 22, 415) studied the velocity of saponification of the amides containing the grouping —CO. CH₂. CO—. They observed that the velocity appeared to depend upon the nature of the radicals attached to the hydrolysable imino group, the position of the methyl group with respect to the imino group and also that the introduction of asymmetry increased the relative rate of hydrolysis.

The present study deals with the rate of saponification of compounds containing the —CO.NH.CO— grouping, viz., acetyl-phenyl, -*m*-tolyl, -*p*-tolyl, -*p*-anisyl, -*p*-xylyl, and -*m*-phenetyl-carbamides and acetylurethane. The results are explained on the basis of the electronic conception of the influence of nuclear substitution on saponification reaction in a side-chain.

EXPERIMENTAL

These substances were prepared by the method given by Desai and Desai (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 249).

Each of the substances (0.00625 g. mole) was dissolved in sufficient alcohol and the volume was made up to 240 c.c. to which 10 c.c. of 2.5*N*-alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution were added, so that the concentration of potassium hydroxide was 0.1 *N* and that of the substance 0.025*M* in the reacting solution (250 c.c.). The saponification was carried out at two different temperatures, viz., 28° and 38°, controlled thermostatically (±0.1°). The excess of alkali was estimated in presence of ice by 0.005 *N* succinic acid by withdrawing 5 c.c. of the reacting solution by means of a pipette at an interval of ten minutes up to 1 hour. In each case each

run was repeated thrice. The bimolecular velocity constant was calculated in terms of litre/g. mol. min. from the equation

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t(a-b)} \log \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)}$$

The energy of activation E was calculated from measurement of the rate constants at the two temperatures by the use of the equation

$$\frac{d \ln k}{dT} = \frac{E}{RT^2}$$

The results of a typical run are given in Table I.

TABLE I

Saponification of acetyl-m-phenetylcarbamide at 28°.

$a = 100$ c.c. $b = 25$ c.c.

Time (t).	Alkali conc. (a-x)	Amide conc. (b-x)	Velocity constant k (in litre/g. mol. min.).
10 min.	94.3 c.c.	19.3 c.c.	0.2665
20	90.2	15.2	0.2629
30	87.0	12.0	0.2642
40	84.4	9.4	0.2696
50	82.5	7.5	0.2699
60	81.0	6.0	0.2704

Mean 0.2672

Table II gives values of rate constants at 28° and 38° and energy of activation E (cals) for different substances.

TABLE II

Sr. No.	Name.	k at 28°.	k at 38°.	E (cals).
1.	Acetylurethane	0.3027	0.7746	17480
2.	Acetyl-m-phenetyl-C*	0.2672	0.7037	18020
3.	Acetylphenyl-C	0.2418	0.6475	18320
4.	Acetyl-m-tolyl-C	0.1318	0.5490	26560
5.	Acetyl-p-tolyl-C	0.1122	0.4811	27080
6.	Acetyl-p-anisyl-C	0.1110	0.4732	26990
7.	Acetyl-p-xylyl-C	0.0983	0.4063	26400

*C denotes carbamide

An examination of the above table reveals that k is of the same order of magnitude thus showing that the mechanism of saponification reaction is the same for different substances. However, the temperature coefficients in some cases are abnormally high; this is rather exceptional in reaction kinetics and requires further investigation at three or four different temperatures. Nevertheless, the results are explained as regards the effect of nuclear substitution on the rate constants of saponification of different substances.

mide (3). In (4), the electronegativity of R' will be decreased through the inductive effect (+I) of -CH₃ group and therefore, lowers the rate than that of (3). While in (5), the rate is still lower, because of the 'tautomeric effect' associated with -CH₃ group in *para* position which will still more decrease the electronegativity of R'. The electron releasing effect of -CH₃ group attached *para* to a phenyl group in (5) is very often due to the hyperconjugative power of the methyl group. In (6), the rate is still lower, because of the greater (+T) effect of -OCH₃ group than that of -CH₃ group in *para* position. The electronegativity of R' is still further reduced in (7) by the (+I) effect of one methyl group in *meta* position and (+T) of the other -CH₃ group in *ortho* position and so of all the ureas, its rate is the lowest. These effects (I and T) may be assumed to be relayed along the chain thus, e.g.,

Again in (1), the rate is maximum as the electronegativity of -OC₂H₅ in ester group is greater than that of -NHR in the amide group.

Thus the effect of the substituents in the phenyl group in various substituted ureas on the side-chain saponification reaction is found to be in the following decreasing order :

The authors express their gratitude to the College Authority for a grant to meet the expenses incurred in this work.